

Homeopathic treatment of migraine: A double blind, placebo controlled trial of 68 patients†

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To evaluate the efficacy of homeopathy in preventing migraine attacks and accompanying symptoms, a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial was conducted. There was a one-month registration period without treatment, followed by four months individualised homeopathic treatment or identical placebo. Patients were stratified for common or classical migraine.

Seventy-three patients were randomised, 68 completed the trial. Baseline values were similar in the two groups. Both the homeopathy and placebo groups had reduction in attack frequency, pain intensity and drug consumption, with a statistically non-significant difference favouring homeopathy. Migraine diaries showed no difference between groups. The neurologists' trial evaluation showed a statistically significant reduction in attack frequency in the homeopathy group ($P=0.04$) and non-statistically significant trends in favour of homeopathy for pain intensity and overall evaluation.

Further research, with improved trial design, on the possible role of homeopathy in migraine prophylaxis is justified. *British Homeopathic Journal* (2000) 89, 4-7.

Keywords: migraine; clinical trial; homeopathy; individualisation

Introduction

Migraine is a common condition. A recent study using the diagnostic criteria of the International Headache Society showed a lifetime prevalence of 16% in the Danish population.¹ 230 Norwegian patients attending general practice had a migraine prevalence of 11%.² In 1993 it was found that migraine is the cause of 4% of sick leave in Norwegian industry.³

There is no complete explanation of the pathophysiology of the condition. Vascular and neurogenic hypotheses can explain some features of the migraine attack, but they cannot explain the quality and complexity of migraine symptoms.⁴ Some propose that we can reach a better understanding of migraine by perceiving it as a protective mechanism. This is

supported by a study of 1504 women with headaches who had less cerebrovascular disease and ischaemic heart disease than expected.⁵

It remains difficult to treat migraine with the poor understanding of pathophysiology. Drug treatment can be divided into two groups, those used acutely to treat attacks, and those used prophylactically. Simple analgesia, ergotamine preparations and lately also sumatriptan are used to curtail attacks. The side effects of ergotamine preparations are problematic and frequent use can increase the frequency of attacks.⁶ Prophylactic treatment, for example with α -blockers, is recommended for those who are disabled for a significant amount of time, roughly equating to two or more attacks per month. Some patients have good results with these treatments, but less than half get 50% or greater reduction of attack frequency.⁷

Homeopaths feel that they can prevent migraine attacks by using their medicines. By stimulating the organism's defence mechanism, they are able to change the established reaction patterns (migraine) to a more favourable way of dealing with stress. In

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an Italian double-blind study, homeopathy was very effective in preventing migraine.⁸

The purpose of this study was to investigate the preventative effects of homeopathic treatment on migraine in a group of patients in a controlled clinical model.

Patients and methods

Patients were recruited via St. Hansenhaugen Medical Centre, mainly after an article about the project. Seventy-three patients between 18 and 65 years with migraine, according to the International Headache Society's classification criteria, were included. They were diagnosed by a neurologist. Inclusion criteria were that the condition should have lasted at least one year, with a frequency of two to six attacks per month over the preceding six months. Pregnant and breast feeding women were excluded together with patients using regular migraine preventative medicines, those with serious hypertension and users of benzodiazepines or hormonal preparations. Patients who abused stimulants or had an illness that made the practical participation in the trial difficult, were excluded. The trial was approved by the regional ethical committee. Assuming the treatment has an effect 70% better than placebo, then 32 patients in each group would provide a statistical power of 0.80, with significance level of 0.05. After inclusion, the patients were block-randomised into a treatment or a placebo group, stratified common (migraine without aura) or classical (migraine with aura) migraine. All patients were issued with a migraine diary, where they were to enter dates of the attacks, pain intensity, length of and the need for medicine for every attack. Pains were plotted on a 100 mm VAS-scale.

After a month of baseline registration, all the patients were interviewed by a homeopathic practitioner, for between one and two hours, to decide upon the homeopathic remedy. The characteristic migraine symptoms, other symptoms that the patient had, general symptoms (e.g. symptoms connected to sleep and appetite) and available psychological symptoms were considered in the remedy choice. An attempt was made to find what a homeopath would classify as a constitutional remedy for the patient after a total assessment. The potency and dose were individually decided upon.

DCG Pharmaceutical AS, Goteborg, made 60 different homeopathic medicines for the trial. Every remedy was provided in dilutions of D30, D200 (30X, 200X) and 1M in identical form and quantity with identical looking placebos, in glass bottles. All the medicine bottles were coded by a statistician who was otherwise uninvolved with the trial. Nobody else who was involved in the trial had access to the code, apart from a pharmacist, who was responsible for the storage and distribution of the medicine and placebo.

After one month of treatment and data registration, the patients came back to the homeopath. A new homeopathic assessment was conducted to decide whether the patients should continue, stop or change medicine. The homeopath noted whether the patients' symptoms had worsened or attacks were more frequent, which could be interpreted as an initial aggravation (an increase of the symptoms soon after the start of the treatment). The patients that were given placebo the first time were given placebo once again if the homeopath found reason to change the remedy. The treatment part of the study was conducted over a four-month period. Patients noted their attacks in the migraine diary. Every month they had a consultation with the homeopath who would assess their further treatment.

Five months after their inclusion, patients were assessed again by the neurologist, who did not know whether the patient belonged to the treatment or the placebo group. Together with the patient he made the final evaluation of the frequency of the attacks, the level of pain intensity, duration of attacks and whether the need of medicament treatment had changed throughout the period. The neurologist asked the patients whether they had experienced side effects or other problems from the treatment. In addition he made a personal evaluation about whether the patient had deteriorated drastically, deteriorated, remained unchanged, improved or improved dramatically during the treatment period.

Of the 73 included, 68 patients completed the study, 35 in the homeopathic group and 33 in the placebo group. One was excluded as he did not have any attacks in the month before the treatment started, two because of pregnancy after the start of treatment, one because of hypertension and one as she did not attend for follow-up consultations.

Statistics

Continuous variables were analysed with *t*-tests, and discrete with single Chi-square tests. Attack frequency per time unit was calculated and this variable was analysed with the help of repeated measures ANOVA.⁹ Exit values were taken as covariant in the analysis. The premises for the model for ANOVA was tested by using the Jack-knife residual and Cook's *d*. All *P*-values of 0.05 or less were considered as significant. All the *t*-tests were two-tailed.

Results

Table 1 shows the comparison of the groups with regard to migraine type, frequency of attacks and pain intensity in the baseline registration month.

The most commonly used homeopathic medicine (including placebo prescription) were (number of prescriptions in brackets): *Natrum mur* (24), *Ignatia*

Table 1 Comparison of homeopathy and placebo groups at the start of the trial (patients who completed study only)

	Homeopathy group	Placebo group
Patients—women/men (no.)	26/6	27/6
Blood pressure (average)		
Systolic	132	127
Diastolic	76	72
Common (without aura) migraine (no.)	28	26
Classic migraine (no.)	7	7
Attacks per month ^a	5.1 (2.6)	5.5 (2.2)
Intensity on 100-mm VAS scale	53.6 (24.8)	53.9 (24.7)

^aAverage (standard) from baseline registration.

(20), *Carcinosin* (16), *Sepia* (8), *Aurum met* (8), *Sulphur* (6) and *Pulsatilla* (6). The total number of prescriptions was 137, of which 70 were in the homeopathic group and 67 in the placebo group.

Figure 1 shows that the frequency of the attacks, as recorded in the migraine diary, decreased in both groups in relation to baseline values, albeit more in the placebo group in comparison to the homeopathic group, although the difference is not significant ($P=0.54$).

The average pain intensity per attack, by VAS, was more or less unchanged and equally distributed between both groups. With regard to duration of the attacks, this was somewhat shorter in the treatment group, but the difference was not significant.

Use of medicine, mainly ergotamine, showed reduction in both groups, more so in the placebo group. Eleven subjects in each group answered that they experienced discomfort with the treatment. The main problems that arose were more frequent headaches during the first days after starting the treatment. There was no difference between the groups with regard to changes in sleep and energy. There was no difference with regard to possible first time aggravation between the groups, as 17 subjects indicated possible aggravations in the active group against 20 in the placebo group.

Figure 2 shows the neurologist's assessment of the frequency of attacks reported by the patient four months after start of the treatment. In the treatment group, 60% had fewer attacks vs 42% in the placebo group. The difference was statistically significant ($P=0.04$) in favour of the treatment group even though three patients in the treatment group were 'somewhat worse' compared to nobody in the placebo group.

Figure 1 Frequency of attacks recorded in the migraine diary, $n=68$.

Figure 2 Neurologist's assessment of the frequency of attacks five months after starting the trial, $n=68$.

Figure 3 Neurologist's final evaluation of 68 patients.

The level of pain intensity was reduced to 54% in the active group compared to 42% in the placebo group ($P=0.08$).

The drug consumption was reduced in both groups, somewhat more in the active group (52% vs 42%, non-significant).

The neurologist's final assessment of the effect is shown in Figure 3, showing that 54% in the active group improved against 39% in the placebo group, a non-significant difference.

Discussion

The results from the study are conflicting. Assessing the diaries, the groups appear very similar whilst the final evaluation of the neurologist made together with the patients shows a significant effect, at least on attack frequency.

In this study we have not found that homeopathy has an effect over that of placebo in the prophylaxis of migraine. Both groups had a decline in frequency of attacks of approximately 30%. The lack of effect of the homeopathic treatment over that of placebo could be due to the study design where the homeopathic treatment was not isolated from other interventions, such as encouragement to use less ergotamine and coffee and the homeopathic interview itself. In hindsight, these interventions should have been made before the baseline registration started. For example, a homeopath would usually ask a migraine patient to reduce ergotamine preparations before homeopathic remedy is given. This is felt possibly to increase the effect of the homeopathic remedy and to avoid difficulty in interpretation of reactions; is an initial aggravation due to ergotamine withdrawal or to the starting of the homeopathic remedy? One model is the use of placebo in both groups during the basal registration period, as utilised by Reilly in two placebo-controlled

studies of the effects of homeopathic potencies in pollen allergy and allergic asthma.^{10,11}

Another factor in this study that could have obscured the effects of the homeopathic treatment is the fact that 18 patients in the baseline registration period had more than six attacks. One of the inclusion criteria was that the patients should have between two and six attacks on average per month. This means that they had a high consumption of ergotamine preparations, something that might reduce the effect of homeopathic remedies. The recommended procedure to reduce ergotamine consumption and withdrawal is by hospital admission.¹² These patients, equally distributed in both groups, should ideally have been excluded after the baseline registration period, but this would have reduced the power of the trial to 0.75.

A separate analysis where this group was excluded showed that they did not differ materially from the rest and exclusion made no difference to the results.

The neurologist's final evaluation shows more positive results. It is difficult to explain the difference between the neurologist/patient evaluation and diaries. It is possible that verbal assessment provides different information to that acquired by diary-keeping.

Given the demonstrated limitations of this study, it is not surprising that the results were not similar to an earlier study of homeopathy and migraine.⁸ Even though the final evaluation from the neurologist suggested a significant improvement for those who were given homeopathic treatment, the main finding is that simply participating in the study reduced the frequency of attacks, pain intensity and medicament consumption. We believe that the homeopathic method with thorough interviews, guidance and close follow ups can explain a lot of this effect.

Controlled clinical studies with homeopathy are difficult as one must take account of homeopathic characteristics, especially the individualising principle in parallel with the strict scientific study procedures.

We are of the opinion that the result of this study does not justify the conclusion that homeopathy is ineffective in prevention of migraine. With the limita-

tions described above, there is reason to repeat the study with an improved design and with a larger number of patients to reveal more subtle effects than those this study could demonstrate.

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